

now clear that the biotype in Bangladesh is not biotype 1 or 2, but is either 3 or 4. ■

List of BPH-resistant materials. BRRI, 1980.

Variety or line	Origin	Reaction ^a to BPH
ARC6650	India	HR
ARC10550		HR
ARC14529		HR
Sinna Sivappu	Thailand	HR
BR.593-1-1-5	Bangladesh	HR
BR593-46-8-2-1		HR
BR593-46-8-2		HR
BR593-46-8-2-4		HR
IR19661-347	IRRI	HR
IR19661-372	IRRI	HR
BG367-9	Sri Lanka	R
BG379-1		R
BG379-3		R
BR593-1-1-2	Bangladesh	R
BR593-1-1-3		R
BR593-48-8-2-5-3		R
IR13240-10-1	IRRI	R
IR13240-39-3		R
IR13240-1-B		R
IR13240-6-3		R
IR13240-10-1		R
IR13240-83-1		R
IR13426-19-2		R
IR13427-60-1		R
1314632-31-3		R
IR14632-272		R
IR19660-121		R
IR19660-189		R
IR19660-53		R
IR19660-161		R
IR19660-253		R
IR19660-192		R
IR19660-315		R
IR19661-13		R
IR19661-163		R
IR19661-364		R
Hondarwala	Sri Lanka	R

^a HR = highly resistant, R = resistant.

induced salinity.

Three hills were grown in each pot. One set of pots was irrigated with saline water (NaCl + CaCl₂ in 4 to 1 ratio), bringing soil EC_e to around 8 mmho/cm. Another set was irrigated with good quality water (EC-0.95 mmho/cm). CCC at 2,000 ppm and BA at 10 ppm were applied to pot sets as foliar sprays twice between primordial initiation and panicle emergence. Each treatment was replicated three times. Grain yield data indicate significant differences due to variety, salinity level, and growth regulator (see table). Under unsprayed saline conditions, Getu, with a 37.5% reduction from normal conditions, yielded more than Madhu with a 70.2% reduction from normal. However,

the extent of reduction varied under salinity in combination with growth regulator. In Getu, the yield was reduced further (72.4%) with BA but increased slightly (31.7%) with CCC. On the other hand, Madhu showed marked response to growth regulators under salinity, with a 55.3% yield reduction under BA and a 36.2% reduction under CCC. The apparent increase in yield could be attributed to increased grains per panicle and reduced spikelet sterility.

The results suggest that care be exercised in selecting varieties as well as growth regulators for improving productivity under saline situation. Getu, a salt-tolerant variety, did not better its performance when supplemented with growth regulators. ■

Effect of growth regulators and salinity on grain yield and associated characteristics of 2 rice varieties. Karnataka, India, 1974 wet season.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (g/pot)		Productive tillers (no./ pot)		Grain (no. panicle)		Spikelet sterility (%)		1,000-grain wt (g)	
	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu	Getu	Madhu
Control normal	32.8	32.8	24.0	25.0	87	95	24.2	32.9	21.1	18.4
Control saline	19.9	9.5	20.7	16.0	69	61	34.6	35.8	17.5	15.3
BA normal	35.8	31.7	26.0	21.3	82	101	29.1	26.5	21.5	18.1
BA saline	8.8	13.6	16.3	17.3	41	74	46.2	31.0	15.3	14.1
CCC normal	27.8	31.4	18.7	22.0	83	100	28.9	30.1	21.5	18.2
CCC saline	22.0	28.9	19.3	18.7	73	83	29.3	32.3	20.0	14.1
Mean	23.0		20.4		79.1		31.7		17.9	
C.D. 5%										
Variety	1.4		ns		2.8		ns		0.5	
Salinity	1.4		1.5		2.8		1.6		0.5	
Growth regulator	1.7		ns		3.5		2.0		0.6	

^aBA = benzyl adenine. CCC = chloroethyl trimethyl ammonium chloride.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Varietal response to growth regulators under saline conditions

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A pot culture study during the 1974 wet season evaluated the effects of two growth regulators, 2-chloroethyl trimethyl ammonium chloride (CCC) and benzyl adenine (BA), on grain yields of rice varieties Getu and Madhu under

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Effect of seedling age on total plant elongation and internode elongation of deepwater rice

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Five recommended deepwater rice varieties were grown in wooden screening boxes (30 × 30 × 24 cm) for 10, 20, 30, and 40 days. Seedlings were then submerged in 100-cm deep water in con-

crete tanks for 7 days. The boxes were adjusted so that leaf tips were about 50 cm below water level.

The internodes of all varieties elongated as early as 20 days, but plant elongation occurred as early as 10 days. The percentage increase in plant elongation had no positive relation with the total length of internodes produced. Total plant elongation decreased with seedling age, but the number of internodes and their total length increased. The greatest plant elongation was observed in 10-day-old seedlings and the